

Filename	Description
Participant Information Sheet	This document explains to participants, in a question-and-answer format, how the research will be conducted and their rights.
Written Informed Consent Form for Participants	This document states that the participant has read the information sheet and agrees to participate in the research.
Basic Questionnaire	It contains questions and answers about basic information such as occupation, education, and the presence of stress.
THI Questionnaire	Questionnaire on Tinnitus Handicap Inventory
BDI Questionnaire	Questionnaire on Beck Depression Inventory
AAQ-II Questionnaire	Questionnaire on Acceptance and Action Questionnaire-II
PSQI Questionnaire	Korean Version of the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index Questionnaire